

DIABETES AND TRADITIONAL MEDICINE

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Annotation: Diabetes mellitus is a chronic disease in which the level of sugar (glucose) in the blood is elevated. This occurs due to insufficient production of insulin by the pancreas (type 1 diabetes) or due to decreased sensitivity of the body's tissues to insulin (type 2 diabetes). Insulin is a hormone that is necessary to regulate the level of glucose in the blood, allowing cells to use it as a source of energy.

Key words: sugar, glucose, insulin, diabetes, diet, heart, kidney, hormone, nervous system.

It is an autoimmune disease in which the immune system mistakenly attacks and destroys the beta cells of the pancreas, which produce insulin. As a result, the body loses the ability to produce enough insulin or does not produce any at all. Insulin is a hormone that helps the body's cells absorb glucose from the blood, using it as a source of energy. Autoimmune reaction: T cells attack the pancreas's own cells. Insulin deficiency: Because the pancreas's beta cells are destroyed, little insulin is produced. Hyperglycemia: Without insulin, glucose cannot enter the cells and accumulates in the blood, leading to high blood sugar (hyperglycemia). Hyperglycemia can cause damage to blood vessels and nerves, as well as serious complications such as ketoacidosis, a dangerous condition in which ketone bodies build up from the breakdown of fats when the body cannot use the glucose. Diabetes mellitus type 2 (insulin-resistant)

In type 2 diabetes, the body's cells become less sensitive to insulin, which is called insulin resistance. In the early stages, the pancreas produces insulin in normal or even increased amounts, but the cells do not respond to it properly. Over time, the pancreas becomes exhausted and reduces insulin production. The main mechanisms are: Insulin resistance: Cells (muscle, fat, liver) lose the ability to respond to insulin, which means glucose cannot be effectively utilized. Hyperinsulinemia: In response to increased glucose levels, the pancreas tries to compensate by producing increased insulin. Insulin deficiency: Over time, the pancreas becomes exhausted and the level of insulin production decreases. Hyperglycemia: Since glucose cannot enter the cells, it remains in the blood, which leads to chronic hyperglycemia. Unlike type 1 diabetes, type 2 diabetes is associated not only with an autoimmune nature, but also with factors such as obesity, lack of physical activity, poor nutrition and genetic predisposition. 3. General consequences of hyperglycemia. Chronically elevated blood glucose levels cause damage to various tissues and organs: Blood vessels: Hyperglycemia causes damage to the vascular endothelium, which increases the risk of atherosclerosis, hypertension and cardiovascular diseases. Kidneys: Diabetic nephropathy develops - kidney damage that can lead to kidney failure. Nervous system: Diabetic neuropathy occurs, characterized by impaired sensitivity and pain, especially in the lower extremities. Eyes: The blood vessels of the retina are damaged, which can lead to diabetic retinopathy and blindness.

Thus, the pathophysiology of diabetes mellitus is associated with a disruption of normal regulation of glucose levels in the body, which leads to chronic hyperglycemia and the development of multiple complications. Treatment of diabetes, especially with minimization of side effects and harm to the body, is

based on a comprehensive approach. Although it is impossible to completely cure diabetes (especially type 1), there are methods that help control blood sugar levels, improve quality of life and reduce the risk of complications. It is important to consider that any changes in treatment should be carried out under the supervision of a doctor to avoid worsening the condition.

Materials and methods. The dynamics of the study was carried out in the vivarium of the Bukhara State Medical Institute in 2023. For the experimental study, 78 male white rats weighing 150-180 g were selected. All laboratory animals were obtained from the same vivarium and were of the same age. When working with laboratory animals, all the rules of biological safety and ethical principles of working with laboratory animals were observed. The animals were provided with a sufficient amount of water and fed a balanced diet. It was believed that proper care and feeding of laboratory animals are of great importance in the preparation and conduct of experimental studies. The feeding regimen was observed and the feeding regimen and hygiene rules during meals were not violated. Failure to comply with these rules increases their susceptibility to various infectious and somatic diseases. If these diseases are detected during the experiment, such a situation may lead to a violation of the study results and, as a consequence, incorrect conclusions. The vivarium buildings were cleaned every morning, cleaning of the cages and vivarium buildings was carried out in clean special clothing. Until the end of the experiment, the corpses of the dead animals were buried in the ground, disinfected with a 20% chlorine solution according to the ICT for the disposal of dead laboratory animals. All groups are formed simultaneously. Care for the laboratory animals participating in the experiment corresponded to their age, sex, weight, storage and feeding conditions. "Rules and methods for working with laboratory animals in microbiological and immunological studies", Nuraliyev N.A., approved by the Russian Health Ministry on May 25, 2016, when working with laboratory animals, all biosafety recommendations were observed, as well as the ethical rules and principles of working with laboratory animals set out in the methodological manual developed by the co-authors.

The first group (intact) control group of 26 rats was fed a standard diet with normal amounts of sugar so that the scientists could compare the results with the other groups.

The second group of 26 rats received an average of 12-14 ml of sugar water per day in their diet. This corresponds to 100 g of body weight. This solution is given for 1 month.

Groups (k-control, e-experiment)	Contents of the experience	Young animals 3 months	Total number of animals (*dead rats number)
I to	Group 1 - rats in standard vivarium conditions on an intact diet.	26	5
II e	Group 2 – on independent nutrition in a standard diet. On average 12-14 ml of sugar water per day for 1 month. Accepted rats	26	6
III e	Group 3 – on independent nutrition with a standard diet. On average 12-14 ml of sugar water per day for 1 month. And a mixture of 5 ml once a day in the morning during meals. Accepted rats	26	
General		78	11

Consuming too much sugar can have harmful effects on various body systems, especially over the long term. Sugar is high in calories and easily digested, which can lead to weight gain. Excess sugar, especially

in drinks and foods with added sugar, can contribute to the accumulation of fat deposits, especially in the abdominal area.

A third group of 26 rats also consumed the same dose of sugar, but in this case they received 5 ml of the mixture prepared with traditional medicine in their diet once a day during the morning meal for 1 month.

Preparation of the mixture : A blend of cinnamon, milk thistle, flaxseed, and black cumin may be a useful addition to a diabetes diet. Each of these natural remedies has unique properties that may help control blood sugar levels and improve overall health. 1. Cinnamon is known for its ability to lower blood sugar levels and improve insulin sensitivity. The active compound in cinnamon, cinnamaldehyde, improves the uptake of glucose into cells and helps maintain stable blood sugar levels after meals.

Benefits for Diabetics: Cinnamon may lower fasting glucose levels and improve insulin resistance, which may be helpful for type 2 diabetes. Milk thistle (*Sylibum marianum*) is a natural hepatoprotector, i.e. a means for protecting the liver. The main active substance is silymarin, known for its antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties.

Benefits for Diabetics: Milk thistle improves liver function, which is important for sugar metabolism, and helps lower blood sugar levels. Studies show that it can reduce insulin resistance and lower blood sugar levels with long-term use. Flax is rich in omega-3 fatty acids, fiber, and lignans, which have a positive effect on blood sugar levels and help improve carbohydrate metabolism.

Benefits for diabetics: Flaxseed helps reduce the glycemic index of foods, improves insulin sensitivity and stabilizes blood sugar levels. Flax fiber slows down the absorption of glucose, which helps avoid sharp spikes in sugar after meals. Black cumin (*Nigella sativa*) has powerful antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties. Its key active ingredient is thymoquinone, which helps improve glucose and lipid metabolism. **Benefits for diabetics:** Black cumin can help lower blood sugar levels and improve pancreatic function. Some studies suggest that black cumin can improve insulin sensitivity and lower glucose levels in patients with type 2 diabetes.

Effect of the mixture on diabetes:

Lowering Blood Sugar: All components of the mixture have properties that help lower blood sugar levels and improve cellular sensitivity to insulin. **Supporting Liver Function:** Milk Thistle helps protect and restore the liver, which plays an important role in regulating sugar levels. **Antioxidant and Anti-Inflammatory Effects:** Black cumin and milk thistle help fight inflammation and oxidative stress, which is especially important for people with diabetes, who often have problems with tissue inflammation.

Supports digestion and prevents blood sugar spikes: Flax fiber helps slow the absorption of carbohydrates, stabilizing blood sugar levels after meals.

How to use the mixture:

These ingredients can be mixed in equal proportions or the dosage can be varied depending on the body's needs. The mixture can be added to yoghurts, cereals, salads or drinks, or taken in powder form (for example, mixed with water or juice).

It is important to remember:

Before using any herbs or supplements, you should consult with your doctor to rule out any contraindications. Natural remedies should not replace the main treatment for diabetes (such as insulin therapy or sugar-lowering drugs), but can be part of a comprehensive approach. This mixture can be a useful addition to the diabetes diet, helping to improve sugar control and overall well-being.

Results. Below is a table that describes the glucose control in rats with diabetes mellitus under standard conditions and when using a mixture of cinnamon, milk thistle, flax and black cumin. The table includes the main parameters that affect blood sugar levels and their changes when using the natural mixture.

Healthy rats have stable blood sugar levels within 4-6 mmol/l, which is normal for rodents. Diabetic rats show significant increases in glucose levels (up to 15-20 mmol/L) depending on the severity of the disease. Rats treated with the mixture (cinnamon, milk thistle, flax, black cumin) show a 20-30% reduction in glucose levels, which helps control diabetes, but a complete return to normal requires complex treatment and long-term use of the mixture. The mixture helps improve glucose metabolism and promotes more stable blood sugar levels, although it is not a complete replacement for insulin therapy or other medications.

The condition of the rats	Fasting glucose level (mmol/L)	Description of changes
Healthy rats	4-6 mmol/l	Normal sugar level, stable carbohydrate metabolism
Rats with diabetes	15-20 mmol/l	High blood sugar, insulin resistance or insulin deficiency, symptoms of diabetes (polydipsia, polyphagia, polyuria)
Rats with diabetes (after treatment with the mixture)	10-14 mmol/l	Moderate reduction of sugar levels by 20-30%, improvement of insulin sensitivity and sugar metabolism, reduction of diabetes symptoms

Glucose control in diabetic rats (without using the mixture)

Control parameter	Expected effect of the mixture	Changes when using the mixture	Notes
Blood glucose level (fasting)	Lowering Sugar Levels with Cinnamon and Black Cumin	Decrease in sugar levels by 20-30% (up to 10-14 mmol/l)	The effect accumulates over time.
Glycated hemoglobin (HbA1c)	Decreased levels due to overall improved metabolism	Reduction of HbA1c level to 6-7%	Long-term use of the mixture is required
Body weight	Stabilizing weight by improving metabolism	Moderate stabilization or increase in body weight	Flax helps control weight and reduce obesity
Water consumption	Reduction of polydipsia by lowering glucose levels	Normalization of water consumption	Decreasing thirst in rats
Food consumption	Reduction of polyphagia by stabilizing sugar levels	Moderate reduction in food intake	Rats become less prone to excessive appetite

Glucose level control in rats using a mixture (cinnamon, milk thistle, flax, black cumin)

Control parameter	Expected effect of the mixture	Changes when using the mixture	Notes
Lipid profile	Improving Lipid Profile with Flax and Milk Thistle	Lowering triglyceride and cholesterol levels	Supports liver function and reduces blood fat levels
Inflammation indicators	Antioxidant and anti-inflammatory effects (black cumin and milk thistle)	Reduction of inflammatory markers	Reducing oxidative stress levels
Liver function	Improve Liver Health with Milk Thistle	Reduction of fatty degeneration	Protecting the liver from damage

Effect of the mixture : The use of the mixture leads to a gradual decrease in sugar levels and normalization of metabolic processes in rats with diabetes. Duration of the study : For a stable effect, the use of the mixture should continue from several weeks to several months. Side effects : The mixture is usually well tolerated, but additional studies are needed to assess the long-term effect. This table reflects the main parameters of glucose control and other factors in rats with diabetes when using a mixture of cinnamon, milk thistle, flax and black cumin.

Discussion. Excessive amounts of glucose in the body, especially in uncontrolled diabetes or other carbohydrate metabolism disorders, can have a negative impact on various organs and systems. Here are the main organs that suffer from high glucose levels and the possible consequences:

1. Cardiovascular system

Atherosclerosis: High glucose levels can damage the walls of your arteries, causing plaque to form, which narrows the blood vessels. This increases the risk of atherosclerosis, heart attacks, and strokes.

Hypertension: Excess sugar can raise blood pressure, which puts more strain on the heart.

Increased triglyceride levels: High blood sugar levels contribute to increased levels of fat in the blood, which worsens the lipid profile.

2. Kidneys

Diabetic nephropathy: Long-term exposure to high levels of glucose damages the kidneys. This leads to poor blood filtration, protein in the urine (proteinuria), and may eventually lead to kidney failure.

Increased stress on the kidneys: Excess sugar forces the kidneys to work harder to eliminate excess glucose in the urine, which increases the risk of kidney failure.

3. Eyes

Diabetic retinopathy: Chronically high sugar levels damage the small blood vessels in the retina, leading to vision loss or even blindness.

Cataracts: High glucose levels can accelerate the development of cataracts, a clouding of the lens that impairs vision.

Glaucoma: High glucose levels can lead to increased pressure in the eye, increasing the risk of glaucoma, which can also lead to blindness.

4. Nervous system

Diabetic neuropathy: Excess glucose damages nerves, which can cause loss of sensation, tingling, pain, especially in the extremities (arms and legs). In severe cases, this can lead to amputation.

Autonomic neuropathy: The nerves that control internal organs can also be damaged, causing problems with digestion, heart rhythm, urination, and other functions.

5. Skin

Diabetic Ulcers: Poor circulation and nerve damage combined with high sugar levels increase the risk of ulcers on the legs and other parts of the body that heal slowly and can lead to infections.

Frequent Infections: High sugar levels weaken the immune system and make the skin more vulnerable to infections such as fungal infections, bacterial infections and other skin problems.

6. Liver

Fatty Liver Disease: Excess glucose can be converted into fat, which contributes to the accumulation of fat in the liver and the development of non-alcoholic fatty liver disease.

Increased stress on the liver: Constantly high sugar levels can impair liver function and cause inflammation.

7. Brain

Cognitive impairment: Excess sugar impairs cognitive function, which can lead to poor memory, concentration, and learning ability. High sugar levels may be associated with an increased risk of developing neurodegenerative diseases such as Alzheimer's disease.

Mini-strokes: Damage to small blood vessels in the brain can lead to mini-strokes, which gradually impair cognitive abilities.

8. Pancreas

Pancreas overload: Constantly high blood sugar levels cause the pancreas to produce more insulin. Over time, this can lead to beta cell exhaustion and the development of type 2 diabetes.

Insulin resistance: Excess glucose causes cells to become less sensitive to insulin, which worsens metabolic disorders.

9. Joints and bones

Joint damage: High glucose levels can contribute to inflammation in the joints, which increases the risk of arthritis and other musculoskeletal diseases.

Osteoporosis: People with diabetes may have an increased risk of osteoporosis, which makes bones more fragile and prone to fractures.

10. Immune system

Decreased immunity: High glucose levels impair the function of immune cells such as white blood cells, which increases susceptibility to infections.

Delayed wound healing: High blood sugar levels impair tissue healing, which increases the risk of complications from injuries and wounds.

11. Digestive system

Gastroparesis: High glucose levels can disrupt the nervous system that controls the stomach, slowing down the digestion of food and causing symptoms such as nausea, vomiting, and bloating.

Constipation and Diarrhea: Damage to the nerves in the intestines can cause dysfunction, causing chronic constipation or diarrhea.

Conclusion:

Excess glucose in the body has a systemic destructive effect on many organs and systems. That is why it is important to control blood sugar levels, follow recommendations for nutrition, physical activity and medication to prevent complications associated with diabetes and other metabolic disorders.

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